

Contribution of green manure in controlling the loss of applied fertilizer nitrogen from rainfed ricesoil

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This field study evaluated the efficiency of green manure to restrict loss of applied fertilizer N through successive nitrification and denitrification. A factorially randomized block design with three replications was done using IR36 in 1991 on a sandy loam soil (pH 7.5; organic C, 0.40%, total N, 0.04%; CEC, 9.4 meq 100 g⁻¹ soil). It was repeated in 1992 with IET5656 on a silty loam soil (pH 7.7; organic C, 0.53%; total N, 0.05%; and CEC, 12.6 meq 100 g⁻¹ soil) at Kalyani (22° 53' N, 88° 31' E). Six-week-old *Sesbania rostrata*, a stem-nodulating green manure, was incorporated at 3 kg m⁻² into half of the 1 × 1-m plots and seedlings transplanted 5 d later. The plots received 100 kg N (as ¹⁵N enriched urea; 5% AE) in three splits, i.e. 70 kg basal, 20 kg at 40 d after

transplanting (DT.) and 10 kg at 80 DT; 26.4 kg P (basally as single superphosphate); and 33.2 kg K (basally as muriate of potash). Four different rainfall conditions were maintained by imposing moisture stress using polyethylene sheets to intercept rain and constant monitoring with field tensiometers.

Drought increased both leaching and gaseous losses of fertilizer ¹⁵N over continuous submergence (Table 1). Green manure significantly reduced both leaching and gaseous losses of fertilizer ¹⁵N and remained most efficient under drought prevailing at the vegetative stage. Maximum reduction in gaseous losses of fertilizer ¹⁵N through green manure was 66.31% in sandy loam soil under drought at the reproductive stage of IET5656. Savings of fertilizer N were reflected in rice grain yield, registering a maximum of 4.20 t ha⁻¹ (IR36) and 8.09 t ha⁻¹ (IET5656) under continuous submergence with green manure. Maximum leaching loss under vegetative-stage drought limited the grain yields to 1.9 t ha⁻¹ (IR36) and 4.8 t ha⁻¹ (IET5656). Drought imposed at maturation did

Table 2. Economic aspects of using green manure in rainfed rice. West Bengal, India. 1991-92.^a

Moisture status	Additional expenditure for green manure use (US\$ ha ⁻¹)	Additional income from green manuring (US\$ ha ⁻¹)		
		Rice grain yield	Fertilizer N saved	Net profit
Continuous submergence	7.20	164.40	9.92	167.12
Drought at vegetative stage	7.20	18.00	8.48	19.28
Drought at reproductive stage	7.20	164.40	10.68	167.88
Drought at maturation stage	7.20	182.40	11.56	186.76

^a Av of 2 yr (1991-92).

not change the grain yields from continuous submergence, and thus conservation of irrigation water can be encouraged at this stage without hampering yield. Green manure significantly increased the grain yields of rice varieties, registering maximum increments of 57.59% (IR36) and 42.87% (IET5656) under drought during the vegetative stage. Drought at any growth stage was harmful to N economy. The use of green manure recovers fertilizer ¹⁵N losses from rainfed rice soil to a great extent and stimulates yield to benefit the economy of rainfed rice farming by a margin of US\$19.28 to US\$186.76 ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ (Table 2) under various rainfall conditions. ■

Routine research. Reports of screening trials of varieties, fertilizer, cropping methods, and other routine observations using standard methodologies to establish local recommendations are not ordinarily accepted. Examples are single-season, single-trial field experiments. Field trials should be repeated across more than one season, in multiple seasons, or in more than one location as appropriate. All experiments should include replications and an internationally known check or control treatment.

Table 1. Yield and fertilizer N losses of rainfed rice as affected by green manure. West Bengal, India. 1991-92.

Moisture status	Manure ^a	Leaching losses of fertilizer ¹⁵ N beyond 30 cm depth of soil (kg ha ⁻¹)		Gaseous losses of fertilizer ¹⁵ N (kg ha ⁻¹)		Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	
		Sandy loam (1991)	Silty loam (1992)	Sandy loam (1991)	Silty loam (1992)	IR36 (1991)	IET5656 (1992)
Continuous submergence	GM	25.59 (18.08)	37.82 (48.28)	8.01(55.20)	6.32 (78.70)	4.2(31.7)	8.1(27.2)
	C	31.24	35.04	17.88	29.67	3.2	6.4
Drought at vegetative stage	GM	17.71 (52.13)	25.93 (48.28)	22.40 (8.38)	27.97 (20.65)	3.0(57.6)	6.9(42.9)
	C	37.00	50.14	24.45	35.25	1.9	4.8
Drought at reproductive stage	GM	34.99 (12.50)	29.14 (31.04)	6.16(66.31)	17.77 (40.45)	3.0(54.9)	7.0(31.9)
	C	39.99	42.26	18.34	29.84	1.9	5.3
Drought at maturation stage	GM	28.20 (12.99)	32.33 (2.03)	13.56(34.78)	4.48 (82.70)	4.1(38.0)	8.1(31.2)
	C	32.41	33.00	20.79	25.89	3.0	6.2
C.D. (at 5%)							
Manure		2.185	3.840	5.548	4.649	0.745	0.225
Moisture		4.089	ns	10.330	ns	ns	0.420
Interaction		2.677	10.159	ns	12.300	ns	ns

^a GM = green manure, C = control. ^b Figures in parentheses indicate percent change over control. Av of three replications.